

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE LEVEL OF INTERLEUKIN 17 AND TESTOSTERONE HORMONE IN MEN'S WITH TOXOPLASMOSIS

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Abstract: Parasitic infection is considered harmful, and the virulence of parasites varies among them in their effect on the human body. Men infected with the Toxoplasma parasite were studied and the effect of the parasite on male fertility was observed. Semen were collected from patients suffering from infertility, as well as the control group, from the infertility center at Al-Sadr Teaching Hospital. The results showed a significant decrease in the quantity of sperm, sperm motility, the normal shape of the sperm, and sperm vitality. The results also showed a significant increase in the level of interleukin 17 for patients infected with the Toxoplasma parasite. The results showed a significant decrease in the level of the hormone testosterone. The results showed that there is an inverse relationship between interleukin 17 and parameters. Semen as well as with the hormone testosterone. It is possible to say that the negative effect of the parasite has a negative impact on men from a fertility standpoint, due to low levels of testosterone, weak immunity, or a change in sperm quality, which may lead to other problems.

Keywords: Sperm parameter, Toxoplasmosis, hormone testosterone, IL17.

Introduction

Toxoplasmosis is a zoonotic disease caused by the protozoan parasite *Toxoplasma gondii* (1,2). It is common among humans and other warm-blooded animals. It infects most animals and birds, but it can only complete its reproductive cycle in cats, as cats are the main host for this type of parasite, This parasite spreads throughout the world and anyone can become infected with it(3,4).

It is found in cat feces and undercooked meat contaminated with the parasite and is transmitted through contact with cats and contaminated foods. It can be transmitted from soil and water to plants, animals and humans (5). It is also transmitted from the mother to her child during pregnancy (6,7). Infection with toxoplasmosis during pregnancy may lead to miscarriage and the birth of a child with birth defects. It also affects men, as it reduces fertility in men (8). It was found that this parasite harms the number and movement of sperm (9,10). It was also found in a study on parasite and male fertility indicated that there is an inverse relationship between their presence and the quality of sperm (11,12).

Interleukin 17 is a pro-inflammatory cytokine. This cytokine is produced by a population of helper T cells known as Th17 cells in response to their stimulation with IL-23 (13). Th17 was originally identified in 1993 with the isolation of IL17 from a rodent T-cell hybridoma (14).IL-17 is a 155 amino acid protein that is a disulfide-linked, homologous secreted glycoprotein (15). IL-17 is unique in that it is unlike any other known

interleukins. Furthermore, IL-17 bears no similarity to any other known proteins or structural domains (16,17).

Among the immune regulatory functions of IL-17 are cytokines, likely due to its induction of several immune signaling molecules. The most prominent role of IL-17 is its involvement in stimulating and mediating proinflammatory responses (18). IL-17 is commonly associated with allergic responses. IL-17 stimulates the production of many other cytokines, chemokines, and prostaglandins from many cell types (19,20).

IL-17 works with IL-22 to induce the expression of antimicrobial peptides by keratinocytes, Cytokine release has many functions, such as airway remodeling, which is a feature of IL-17 responses. Increased expression of chemokines attracts other cells including neutrophils (21,22). IL-17 has been linked to several immune/autoimmune-related diseases including rheumatoid arthritis, asthma, lupus, allograft rejection, antitumor immunity, and more recently psoriasis (23).

researcher examining the role of IL 17 has indicated a very important role for local tissue disease in IL 17's effect of releasing pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines. In addition, another researcher presented interleukin 17, which stimulates some genes responsible for the production of growth factors and some peptides that stimulate some microbes. Another researcher also presented interleukin 17, which stimulates the formation of neutrophils (24,25).

This study aimed to determine the relationship between interleukin 17 and testosterone levels and its effect on infertile men.

Materials and Methods

The patient was selected after examination for the presence of toxoplasma infection. Semen were collected from patients suffering from infertility, as well as the control group, from the infertility center at Al-Sadr Teaching Hospital. Microscopic analysis has been used to classify infertility cases. The average age of the patients was (35±32) years. Seventy patient samples, 25 control group samples, and a total of 90 samples were collected. Use an ELISA device (original from Germany) to measure the level of Interleukin 17 as well as testosterone. Each test was conducted at the College of Science at the University of Kufa.

The Result

The results showed a decrease in Level of sperm count in toxoplasmosis patients compared to healthy people. The results also showed a decrease in sperm motility, Sperm normal morphology and sperm Viability in toxoplasmosis patients compared to healthy people.

Testosterone levels decreased significantly in men with toxoplasmosis compared to the control group. In addition, the results indicate a positive relationship between testosterone levels and sperm parameters

While interleukin 17 levels increased significantly in men with toxoplasmosis compared to the control group. In addition, the results indicate a significant negative relationship between IL17 levels and sperm parameters and testosterone hormone.

Table (1): Semen and sperm parameters for men with toxoplasmosis compared to the control group

Studied parameters	men with toxoplasmosis	control group
Sperm count million /ml	11 ± 0.61*	63.31± 3.21
Sperm progressive motile	15.41± 0.32*	70.17±1.15
Sperm normal morphology	10.36± 0.29 *	65.45± 1.21
Viability sperm test	10.28± 0.58*	80.83± 0.11

The results inside the table represent mean± Std. Error,

* Denotes significant (P <0.05)

FIGURE1. comparison of IL17 level in the serum between men with toxoplasmosis compared with control group., difference later indicates significant (p < 0.05)

FIGURE2. comparison of testosterone hormone level in the serum between men with toxoplasmosis compared with control group.,

* indicates significant (p < 0.05)

Table (2): The correlation between Interleukin 17 with sperm parameters in men's with toxoplasmosis

Interleukin 17 with Sperm count	R= - 0.752
Interleukin17 with Sperm progressive motile	R = - 0.843
Interleukin 17 with Sperm normal morphology	R =- 0.756
Interleukin 17 with Viability sperm	R= - 0.813
Interleukin 17 with testosterone hormone	R = - 0.941

Table (3): The correlation between testosterone hormone with sperm parameters in men's with toxoplasmosis

Testosterone hormone with Sperm count	R= + 0.967
Testosterone hormone with Sperm progressive motile	R = + 0.933
Testosterone hormone with Sperm normal morphology	R = + 0.966
Testosterone hormone with Viability sperm	R= + 0.923

Discussion

Most semen parameters of infected patients vary, and the changes caused by the parasite in the host endocrine system may be a possible mechanism for changing men's behaviors and endocrine glands, which negatively affects sperm count and quality (26,27). Testosterone is an important factor influencing behavior and personality in men, and it was found that there is a significant decrease in men infected with the parasite. The reason may be due to a hormonal imbalance resulting from the infection (28,29,30). Interestingly, there is a significant increase in interleukin 17 levels for men with toxoplasmosis, and the reason may be due to the immune response in the body caused by the parasite and its effect on the man's body(31,32).

It is possible to say that the negative effect of the parasite has a negative impact on men from a fertility standpoint, due to low levels of testosterone, weak immunity, or a change in sperm quality, which may lead to other problems.

Conclusion

It is possible to say that the negative effect of the parasite has a negative impact on men from a fertility standpoint, due to low levels of testosterone, weak immunity, or a change in sperm quality, which may lead to other problems.

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